

**CUBIC OPERATORS DEFINED ON A SIMPLEX OF IDEMPOTENT
MEASURES**

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Abstract: In this paper described some cubic operators which map the $(n-1)$ -dimensional simplex of idempotent measures to itself. Such operators are divided to two classes: the first class contains all $n \times n \times n \times n$ - matrices with positive entries which for each l -th cubic matrix exists number $\exists m_l \leq n$, where all of the elements of the l -th ($l \leq n$) cubic matrix are zeroes except elements as $p_{ijm_l, l}$, $p_{im_l, j, l}$ and $p_{m_l, ij, l}$; the second class contains all $n \times n \times n \times n$ - matrices with positive entries which has at least one cubic matrix. These matrices play a role of the stochastic matrices in the case of idempotent measures. For both classes of cubic operators we find fixed points and their characters.

Key words: cubic operator, simplex, idempotent measure, fixed point, attracting fixed point, repelling fixed point.

1. INTRODUCTION.

In this paper, we consider the simplex I_n of idempotent measures on $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, where

$$I_n = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in R_{\max}^n : \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} x_i = 0\} = \\ = \{(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in R_{\max}^n : x_1 \oplus x_2 \oplus \dots \oplus x_n = 1\}$$

and consider cubic maps of I_n to itself. The term idempotent measure in our case is used in the sense of idempotent analysis ([1, 2, 3]) rather than in the sense of abstract harmonic analysis as in [4].

In [5] linear maps of the set of idempotent measures are constructed and their dynamical systems are studied. The quadratic operators defined on the set of

idempotent measures which we shall consider in this paper are “idempotent” analogies of quadratic stochastic operators of [6].

In [7] we found construction of quadratic operators given by cubic matrices. In [8] studied fixed points and their characters of these quadratic operators case $n=2$ and their trajectories are constructed.

In [9] described quadratic operators which map I_n to itself and studied fixed points of these operators in case $n=3$.

In [10] constructed dynamics of quadratic operators defined on a three dimensional simplex of idempotent measures.

In this paper we will continue researches which studied in works [7,8,9,10].

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we describe all cubic operators which map the $(n-1)$ -dimensional simplex of idempotent measures to itself. Such operators are divided to two classes. Section 3 contains a description of fixed points for both classes of cubic maps.

2. CUBIC OPERATORS WHICH MAP I_n TO ITSELF

In this section we shall answer the question: which cubic operator maps I_n to itself?

Definition. The $P: x \rightarrow x'$ mapping is called a cubic operator if the following equality is satisfied:

$$x'_l = \sum_{i,j,k=1}^n p_{ijk,l} x_i x_j x_k \quad (1)$$

The following theorem describes such quadratic maps. For the matrix $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^n$ a fixed $l \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ the matrix $(p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k=1}^n$ is called the l -th cubic matrix.

Theorem 1. A cubic operator $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^n$ with $p_{ijk,j} \geq 0$ maps I_n to itself if and only if it satisfies one of following conditions:

i) For each l -th ($l \leq n$) cubic matrix of the operator $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^n$ exists number $\exists m_l \leq n$, where all of the elements of the l -th ($l \leq n$) cubic matrix are zeroes except elements as $p_{m_l j k, l}$, $p_{i m_l k, l}$ and $p_{i j m_l, l}$. Where $m_r \neq m_q$ if $r \neq q$, $i = \overline{1, n}$, $j = \overline{1, n}$, $k = \overline{1, n}$, $l = \overline{1, n}$;

ii) Cubic operator $P = (p_{ki,j})_{i,j,k=1}^n$ has at least one zero cubic matrix. ($\exists m \leq n$ such that the m -th cubic matrix consists of only zeroes, e.g. $p_{ijk,m} = 0$, where $i = \overline{1, n}$, $j = \overline{1, n}$, $k = \overline{1, n}$).

Let's denote by $P_{(n;m_1,m_2,\dots,m_n)}$ operator $\mathbf{P}$ as

$$P_{(n;m_1,m_2,\dots,m_n)} = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^n \quad (2)$$

where n – order of the cubic operator, m_l – is the number which corresponding to the l -th cubic matrix of the cubic operator $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^n$, $m_l \leq n$, $m_r \neq m_q$, $r \neq q$.

In (2) we can see that there are $n!$ cases possible. It will be too difficult to analysis all of these cases. That's why according to the form (2) we can make the set A as:

$$A = \{m_l \mid m_l = l, l = \overline{1, n}\} \quad (3)$$

For $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ from (2) and (3) we'll get following results:

1) if $n = 2$ i.e., operator $P: I_2 \rightarrow I_2$ has two cases:

1.1) $|A| = 2$ if $P_{(2;1,2)}$ so $m_1 = 1$, $m_2 = 2$;

1.2) $|A| = 0$ if $P_{(2;2,1)}$ so $m_1 = 2$, $m_2 = 1$.

2) if $n = 3$ i.e., operator $P: I_3 \rightarrow I_3$ has three cases:

2.1) $|A| = 3$ if $P_{(3;1,2,3)}$;

2.2) $|A| = 1$ if $P_{(3;1,3,2)}$, $P_{(3;2,1,3)}$ and $P_{(3;3,2,1)}$;

2.3) $|A| = 0$ if $P_{(3;2,3,1)}$ and $P_{(3;3,1,2)}$.

Analogically, for the second condition of the theorem 1 we can denote the set B as:

$$B = \left\{ w_l \mid \text{all of the elements of the } l\text{-th cubic matrix are zeroes, } l = \overline{1, n} \right\} \quad (4)$$

For $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ from (4) we'll get following results:

1) if $n = 2$ i.e., operator $P : I_2 \rightarrow I_2$ has two cases:

1.1) $|B| = 1$, e.g., $B = \{w_1\}$ and $B = \{w_2\}$;

1.2) $|B| = 2$, e.g., $B = \{w_1, w_2\}$.

2) if $n = 3$ i.e., operator $P : I_3 \rightarrow I_3$ has three cases:

2.1) $|B| = 1$, e.g., $B = \{w_1\}$, $B = \{w_2\}$ and $B = \{w_3\}$;

2.2) $|B| = 2$, e.g., $B = \{w_1, w_2\}$, $B = \{w_1, w_3\}$ and $B = \{w_2, w_3\}$;

2.3) $|B| = 3$, e.g., $B = \{w_1, w_2, w_3\}$.

3. Fixed points of P.

Recall that fixed points of $P : I_n \rightarrow I_n$ are solutions to $P(x) = x$. Denote by $Fix(P)$ the set of all fixed point of P . Let's find fixed points of cubic operator $P : I_2 \rightarrow I_2$.

Proposition 1. If $n = 2$ and condition (i) of the theorem 1 is satisfied, then the set of the solutions of the equation $P(x) = x$ will have the following form:

$$Fix(P) = \begin{cases} \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) & \text{if } |A| = 2, p_{111,1} \neq 0; \\ \left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right) & \text{if } |A| = 2, p_{222,2} \neq 0; \\ (0, 0) & \text{for all other cases.} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Proof: Assume, P cubic operator is given as: $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^2$. Then by the formula (1) the equation $P(x) = x$ has the form

$$P = \left[\left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} p_{111,1} & p_{121,1} & p_{112,1} & p_{122,1} \\ p_{211,1} & p_{221,1} & p_{212,1} & p_{222,1} \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} p_{111,2} & p_{121,2} & p_{112,2} & p_{122,2} \\ p_{211,2} & p_{221,2} & p_{212,2} & p_{222,2} \end{array} \right) \right]$$

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = p_{111,1}x_1^3 + (p_{121,1} + p_{112,1} + p_{211,1})x_1^2x_2 + (p_{122,1} + p_{212,1} + p_{221,1})x_1x_2^2 + p_{222,1}x_2^3 \\ x_2 = p_{111,2}x_1^3 + (p_{121,2} + p_{112,2} + p_{211,2})x_1^2x_2 + (p_{122,2} + p_{212,2} + p_{221,2})x_1x_2^2 + p_{222,2}x_2^3 \end{cases}$$

(6)

Let P satisfies condition (i) of theorem 1 then we have two cases: $P_{(2;1,2)}$ and $P_{(2;2,1)}$ as:

$$P_{(2;1,2)} = \left[\left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} p_{111,1} & p_{121,1} & p_{112,1} & p_{122,1} \\ p_{211,1} & p_{221,1} & p_{212,1} & 0 \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} 0 & p_{121,2} & p_{112,2} & p_{122,2} \\ p_{211,2} & p_{221,2} & p_{212,2} & p_{222,2} \end{array} \right) \right]$$

$$P_{(2;2,1)} = \left[\left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} 0 & p_{121,1} & p_{112,1} & p_{122,1} \\ p_{211,1} & p_{221,1} & p_{212,1} & p_{222,1} \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} p_{111,2} & p_{121,2} & p_{112,2} & p_{122,2} \\ p_{211,2} & p_{221,2} & p_{212,2} & 0 \end{array} \right) \right]$$

1a) Let P satisfies condition (i) of theorem 1 and $m_l = 1$ e.g., $|A| = 2$ and $P_{(2;1,2)}$.

Then by (6) we'll find following system:

$$P_{(2;1,2)} : I_2 \rightarrow I_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = p_{111,1}x_1^3 + (p_{121,1} + p_{112,1} + p_{211,1})x_1^2x_2 + (p_{122,1} + p_{212,1} + p_{221,1})x_1x_2^2 \\ x_2 = p_{222,2}x_2^3 + (p_{121,2} + p_{112,2} + p_{211,2})x_1^2x_2 + (p_{122,2} + p_{212,2} + p_{221,2})x_1x_2^2 \end{cases}$$

Following three cases are possible:

1a.1) Let $x_1 \leq 0, x_2 = 0$ then we get: $\begin{cases} x_1 = p_{111,1}x_1^3 \\ x_2 = 0 \end{cases}$. The solutions are

$$x_2 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}} \quad (p_{111,1} \neq 0) \text{ and } x_1 = 0, \text{ hence the fixed points are } (0, 0) \text{ and } \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right).$$

1a.2) Assume $x_1 = 0, x_2 \leq 0$ then we get $\begin{cases} x_1 = 0 \\ x_2 = p_{222,2}x_2^3 \end{cases}$. The solutions are is $x_2 = 0$

and $x_2 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \quad (p_{222,2} \neq 0)$, hence the fixed points are $(0, 0)$ and $\left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right)$.

1a.3) Let $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ then we get fixed point $(0, 0)$.

1b) Let P satisfies condition (i) of theorem 1 and $m_l \neq l$ e.g., $|A|=0$ and $P_{(2;2,1)}$.

Then by (8) we'll find following system:

$$P_{(2;2,1)} : I_2 \rightarrow I_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = (p_{121,1} + p_{112,1} + p_{211,1})x_1^2 x_2 + (p_{122,1} + p_{212,1} + p_{221,1})x_1 x_2^2 + p_{222,1}x_2^3 \\ x_2 = p_{111,2}x_1^3 + (p_{121,2} + p_{112,2} + p_{211,2})x_1^2 x_2 + (p_{122,2} + p_{212,2} + p_{221,2})x_1 x_2^2 \end{cases}$$

There is at least one zero element in $x=(x_1, x_2)$. So $x_1=0$ or $x_2=0$ then we'll get that $P_{(2;2,1)}$ has only one fixed point as: $(0,0)$.

Proposition 1 is proved.

Proposition 2. If $n=2$ and condition (ii) of the theorem 1 is satisfied, then the set of the solutions of the equation $P(x) = x$ will have the following form:

$$Fix(P) = \begin{cases} \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) \text{ if } B = \{w_2\}, p_{111,1} \neq 0; \\ \left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right) \text{ if } B = \{w_1\}, p_{222,2} \neq 0; \\ (0, 0) \text{ for all other cases.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Proof: Assume, P is given as a cubic matrix: $P = (p_{ijk,l})_{i,j,k,l=1}^2$. Then by the formula (1) the equation $P(x) = x$ has the form

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = p_{111,1}x_1^3 + (p_{121,1} + p_{112,1} + p_{211,1})x_1^2 x_2 + (p_{122,1} + p_{212,1} + p_{221,1})x_1 x_2^2 + p_{222,1}x_2^3 \\ x_2 = p_{111,2}x_1^3 + (p_{121,2} + p_{112,2} + p_{211,2})x_1^2 x_2 + (p_{122,2} + p_{212,2} + p_{221,2})x_1 x_2^2 + p_{222,2}x_2^3 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Let P satisfies condition (ii) of theorem 1 then two cases are possible:

2a) Let P satisfies condition (ii) of theorem 1 and $|B|=1$ e.g., $B = \{w_1\}$ and $B = \{w_2\}$.

$$B = \{w_1\} \Rightarrow P = \left[\begin{array}{ccc|cc} 0 & 0 & 0 & p_{111,2} & p_{121,2} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & p_{211,2} & p_{221,2} \end{array} \middle| \begin{array}{cc} p_{112,2} & p_{122,2} \\ p_{212,2} & p_{222,2} \end{array} \right]$$

$$B = \{w_2\} \Rightarrow P = \left[\left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} p_{111,1} & p_{121,1} & p_{112,1} & p_{122,1} \\ p_{211,1} & p_{221,1} & p_{212,1} & p_{222,1} \end{array} \right) \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right) \right]$$

Let's check the quadratic operator which $B = \{w_1\}$. Then from (9) we'll find following system:

$$P: I_2 \rightarrow I_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = 0 \\ x_2 = p_{222,2}x_2^3 \end{cases}$$

Following three cases are possible:

2a.1) Let $x_1 \leq 0, x_2 = 0$ then we'll find solution as: $x_1 = 0, x_2 = 0$, hence the fixed point is $(0, 0)$.

2a.2) Assume $x_1 = 0, x_2 \leq 0$ then we get $x_2 = p_{222,2}x_2^3$. The solutions are $x_2 = 0$ and $x_2 = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}}$ ($p_{222,2} \neq 0$), hence the fixed points are $(0, 0)$ and $\left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}}\right)$.

2a.3) Let $x_1 = x_2 = 0$ then we get fixed point $(0, 0)$.

Analogically we can show that points $(0, 0)$ and $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$ are fixed points of the case $B = \{w_2\}$.

2b) Let P satisfies condition (ii) of theorem 1 and $|B| = 2$, e.g., $B = \{w_1, w_2\}$.

$$B = \{w_1, w_2\} \Rightarrow P = \left(\begin{array}{cc|cc} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{array} \right)$$

Then from (10) we'll find following system:

$$P: I_2 \rightarrow I_2 \Rightarrow \begin{cases} x_1 = 0 \\ x_2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

In this case there is only one fixed point as: $(0, 0)$.

Proposition 2 is proved.

From prepositions 1 and 2 we shall get following theorem:

Theorem 2. If $n = 2$ and theorem 1 is satisfied, then $Fix(P)$ the set of all fixed point of cubic operator $P: I_2 \rightarrow I_2$ will have the following form:

$$\text{Fix}(P) = \begin{cases} \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) & \text{if } (|A|=2 \text{ or } B = \{w_2\}) \text{ and } p_{111,1} \neq 0; \\ \left(0, \frac{1}{p_{22,2}} \right) & \text{if } (|A|=2 \text{ or } B = \{w_1\}) \text{ and } p_{22,2} \neq 0; \\ (0, 0) & \text{for all other cases.} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

4. Trajectories of quadratic operators which map of I_2 to itself

When we map the non-fixed points by using quadratic maps they will change their coordinates. In this paper our aim is to find the trajectory of non-fixed points if we use quadratic maps to them so many times. In other words, we should find the solution of the following limit:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(P(P(\dots(P(x))\dots))) \quad (10)$$

For getting the trajectories of quadratic maps of I_2 to itself let's use the results

1a.1 (fixed point is $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$) and **1a.2** (fixed point is $\left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}}\right)$) in Section 3.

These results are found by using quadratic operator $P_{(2;1,2)}$.

In case 1a we will check the points which are situated by the two sides of fixed point $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$. These points we can denote as $\left(-\frac{k}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$. In this case, if $k > 1$

we will get point which situated between points $(-\infty, 0)$ and $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$; if $0 < k < 1$

we will get point which situated between points $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0\right)$ and $(0, 0)$. Then we solve

the expression (10) step by step.

Continuously doing these operations we will get the solution of expression (10) for all natural values of n as:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}(P_{(2;1,2)}(P_{(2;1,2)}(\dots(P_{(2;1,2)}(x))\dots))) = \left(-\frac{k^{3^n}}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right)$$

(11)

From (12) we get conclusion, for $k > 1$, i.e. if the point is on the left from the fixed point in case 1a it will be move to the fixed point $(-\infty, 0)$; for $k < 1$, i.e., if the point is on the right from the fixed point in case 1a it will be move to the fixed point $(0, 0)$.

There are 3 cases possible:

1) for $k > 1$ we will get the point as: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\frac{k^{3^n}}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) = (-\infty, 0);$

2) for $k < 1$ we will get the point as: $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\frac{k^{3^n}}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) = (0, 0);$

3) for $k = 1$ we will get the point as:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\frac{k^{3^n}}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right) = \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right).$$

Analogically, we can see the case 1b. Let $x_1 = 0, x_2 < 0$ then for $\left(0, -\frac{k}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right)$ and

$n = 1$ we will get following result for all natural values of n expression (11) will be defined as:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}^n(x) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P_{(2;1,2)}(P_{(2;1,2)}(P_{(2;1,2)}(\dots(P_{(2;1,2)}(x))\dots))) = \left(0, -\frac{k^{3^n}}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right) \quad (12)$$

5. Conclusion.

There are three markedly different types of fixed points: attracting, repelling and neutral fixed points.

We can see, fixed points $\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{111,1}}}, 0 \right)$ and $\left(0, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{p_{222,2}}} \right)$ are repelling fixed points.

The fixed point $(0, 0)$ is an attracting fixed point.

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